

Drifting Ears on Rivers: A Scalable IoT-Based System for Spatiotemporal Mapping of Anthropogenic Noise Pollution in Freshwater Ecosystems

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Introduction

Background: Anthropogenic noise, particularly vessel noise, dominates large river soundscapes, threatening both aquatic habitat quality and recreational sound environments.

Current research lacks robust field measurement methods to comprehensively assess the spatiotemporal distribution of anthropogenic noise in freshwater ecosystems.

Key Contributions: We developed an integrated workflow encompassing large-scale noise measurement, vessel noise prediction, and spatiotemporal noise mapping in freshwater systems.

Research Area

Noise Drifter

- Controller: **Raspberry Pi PICO**
- Noise Sensor: **MEMS Microphone INMP 441**
- GNSS Module: **Waveshare L76K Multi-GNSS Module**
- IoT Module: **Waveshare SIM7020C**

Workflow

Noise Monitoring: A custom-designed Noise Drifter was developed to collect synchronized underwater noise and GPS location data along large river systems, with real-time data transmission enabled by IoT modules.

Noise Prediction: Utilizing Automatic Identification System (AIS) vessel data (distance d, vessel length L, vessel speed v, direction angle θ) as input, we developed a Graph Convolutional Network (GCN) model to predict spatiotemporal vessel-induced noise patterns across fluvial ecosystems.

Noise Distribution Modeling: Pre-trained GCN model enables real-time generation of high-resolution noise distribution maps by processing live Automatic Identification System (AIS) vessel trajectory data.

Findings

Noise Monitoring: The IoT-enabled drifter system presents a deployable and cost-effective solution for large-scale aquatic noise monitoring applications. The observed noise-level homogeneity (60-100 dBA range) along the 180-km river corridor indicates consistent anthropogenic dominance, with localized exceedances (>100 dBA) marking intense vessel activity zones.

Prediction and Distribution: With important vessel features L, v, d and θ as input, the GCN model demonstrates effective predictive capability ($R^2 = 0.592$), enabling high-resolution (10 m) noise mapping that clearly reveals vessel-dominated acoustic patterns across the waterway. Vessel noise accounts for 60% of total noise exposure.

Contact

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